

COMPARING LLM-GENERATED AND TEACHER FEEDBACK ON MEDICAL ESP WRITING

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Abstract

This study compares teacher and large language model (LLM) feedback on 50 Medical English essays within English for Specific Purposes (ESP) writing assessment. Three conditions were analysed: teacher feedback, AI-minimalist prompting, and AI-structured prompting, with a focus on the effects of prompt engineering on feedback quality. Results show that structured prompt engineering produced the most extensive and detailed feedback, with the highest comment counts, longest comments, and near-complete coverage of the error taxonomy. In contrast, minimalist prompting generated feedback focused primarily on surface-level issues, while teacher feedback prioritised coherence and higher-order concerns. Low overlap between teacher and LLM feedback suggests that these approaches serve complementary roles in writing assessment. The findings highlight the growing role of AI in education, demonstrating that LLM-generated feedback can support scalable and systematic writing assessment in Medical English and ESP contexts, while underscoring the continued importance of human evaluation in pedagogically sensitive environments.

Keywords: *Medical English; Writing assessment; English for Specific Purposes (ESP); Prompt engineering; AI in education*

Introduction

The feasibility of using large language models (LLMs) to generate formative feedback in domain-specific writing was examined because automated systems can produce rapid, detailed annotations but their alignment with teacher judgement requires evaluation. A ten-category

taxonomy (Grammar, Articles, Prepositions, Terminology, Register, Coherence, Spelling, Syntax, Logic, Punctuation) was used to compare original teacher annotations with two prompting strategies: a brief, surface-focused prompt (fig.1, AI-minimalist) and an extended, category-labelled, machine-parsable prompt (fig.2, AI-structured). Prior classroom deployments and student/instructor studies of LLM-generated feedback motivated the design and the focus on faithfulness, specificity, and usability (Escalante et al., 2023; Jia et al., 2024; Meyer et al., 2024).

Give short feedback on the following student text. Point out only the main mistakes and suggest quick fixes.

Student text:

<<<PASTE HERE>>>

Fig.1 – AI-minimalist prompt

You are giving structured feedback on a medical English student essay.

- Identify errors using the 10-category taxonomy (grammar, articles, prepositions, terminology, register, coherence, etc.).
- Quote the part with the error.
- Suggest a correction.
- Give a short reason why it matters.
- At the end, list 2–3 main priorities for revision.

Student text:

<<<PASTE HERE>>>

Fig.2 – AI-detailed prompt

Methods

Fifty essays were randomly sampled from a single cohort of second-year medical students, anonymized, and assigned study IDs. The original teacher comments were retained as the human baseline. Each essay was processed under three conditions: (1) preserved teacher feedback, (2) AI-minimalist prompting (single concise prompt applied uniformly), and (3) AI-structured prompting (extended prompt enforcing category labels, a “Correction:” token, and predictable output format). The same LLM (ChatGPT 5.0) was used for automated conditions and sessions were periodically reset to mitigate session drift. Outputs were parsed into discrete comment units and mapped to the taxonomy; parsing routines were validated against manual inspection on a 10% subsample. The effects of prompt design on scope and format of LLM outputs have been previously demonstrated (Wei et al., 2022).

Materials and Taxonomy

A ten-category error taxonomy was developed for medical ESP to separate surface mechanics from higher-order discourse concerns. Decision rules and coding examples were compiled in a codebook (provided in Supplementary Materials) and were used to map both teacher and model annotations for breadth, frequency, and category-level comparison.

Results

Descriptive statistics for the three feedback conditions are summarised in Table 1. AI-structured feedback produced substantially more comments per essay ($M = 15.10$, $SD = 4.94$) than AI-minimalist ($M = 8.68$, $SD = 5.17$) and teacher feedback ($M = 1.30$, $SD = 0.81$). Average comment length was greatest for AI-structured comments ($M = 353.97$ chars, $SD = 352.59$), intermediate for AI-minimalist ($M = 139.94$ chars, $SD = 49.09$), and smallest for teacher comments ($M = 78.78$ chars, $SD = 34.90$). Coverage of the ten-category taxonomy followed the same ordering: AI-structured reached near-complete coverage ($M = 94.2\%$, $SD = 14.72$), AI-

minimalist produced moderate breadth ($M = 54.0\%$, $SD = 15.39$), and teachers flagged comparatively few taxonomy categories per essay ($M = 19.4\%$, $SD = 11.14$). Correction rate differed dramatically between conditions: AI-structured exhibited a very high proportion of explicit corrective items ($M = 96.23\%$, $SD = 14.53$), whereas AI-minimalist showed a negligible correction-token rate ($M = 0.82\%$, $SD = 5.80$). The teacher correction rate is reported as 0.00% ($SD = 0.00$) under the literal token-counting rule; this is a methodological artifact because teacher corrections were often phrased without the explicit “Correction:” token and therefore were not captured by the automated token rule (see Methods and Discussion).

Category-level coverage (percent of essays in which each taxonomy category was flagged) is presented in Table 2. AI-structured flagged nearly every category in almost all essays ($\approx 98\%$ for Grammar, Articles, Prepositions, Terminology, Register, Coherence, and Punctuation; 94% for Syntax and Logic; 68% for Spelling), reflecting the structured prompt’s explicit instruction to search across all taxonomy categories. AI-minimalist concentrated on surface-level mechanics — Articles (100%) and Punctuation (98%) — while also flagging Grammar (54%) and Syntax (68%) in many essays; lower coverage was observed for Terminology (14%) and Spelling (28%). Teacher feedback showed a distinct profile, with the highest coverage for Coherence (68%), and notable coverage for Articles (38%), Spelling (32%) and Logic (22%), but very low coverage for low-level categories such as Grammar (6%) and Syntax (0%). These patterns indicate that AI-structured produced maximal breadth and explicit corrections by design, AI-minimalist prioritized surface-form mechanics, and teacher feedback concentrated on higher-order, discourse-level issues.

Overlap between teacher-flagged and AI-flagged categories was low. Mean Jaccard similarity between teacher and AI-minimalist category sets was approximately 0.194 , and between teacher and AI-structured was approximately 0.189 , indicating only modest intersection in what teachers and models flagged. Taken together, the descriptive and set-overlap results suggest complementary roles for teachers and LLM feedback: structured LLM prompts yield comprehensive, corrective,

and machine-readable annotations, minimal prompts yield efficient surface-level editing cues, and teachers supply higher-order, contextualized guidance that is not well captured by either AI condition under the present operationalisation. Low set overlap between teacher and AI flags suggested complementary, rather than redundant, behaviours (Jia et al., 2024; Escalante et al., 2023).

Table 1

Descriptive metrics (per condition)
(Mean \pm SD; coverage reported as proportion of 10 taxonomy categories flagged)

Condition	mean_comment_count (SD)	mean_avg_len (chars) (SD)	mean_coverage (%) (SD)	mean_correction_rate (%) (SD)
AI-minimalist	8.68 (5.17)	139.94 (49.09)	54.0% (15.39)	0.82% (5.80)
AI-structured	15.10 (4.94)	353.97 (352.59)	94.2% (14.72)	96.23% (14.53)
Teacher	1.30 (0.81)	78.78 (34.90)	19.4% (11.14)	0.00% (0.00)*

Table 2

Category coverage (percent of essays where category was flagged by condition)

Category (taxonomy)	Teacher (%)	AI-minimalist (%)	AI-structured (%)
Grammar	6.0	54.0	98.0
Articles	38.0	100.0	98.0
Prepositions	2.0	38.0	98.0
Terminology	14.0	14.0	98.0
Register	2.0	52.0	98.0
Coherence	68.0	66.0	98.0
Spelling	32.0	28.0	68.0
Syntax	0.0	68.0	94.0
Logic	22.0	22.0	94.0
Punctuation	10.0	98.0	98.0

Fig. 3 – Category coverage percentages by condition

Discussion

A consistent divergence in behavior was observed: structured prompting elicited comprehensive, machine-parsable, and corrective annotations; brief prompting produced efficient surface-level editing cues; and teachers provided selective, context-sensitive, higher-order guidance. These prompt-dependent differences align with evidence that prompting strategy and schema enforcement materially change the scope and format of model output (Wei et al., 2022). Practically, a curated hybrid workflow was recommended in which LLM-structured passes surface candidate mechanical and mid-level issues in a predictable format while teachers triage and contextualize items that require pedagogical judgement (Escalante et al., 2023; Meyer et al., 2024; Jia et al., 2024).

Limitations and risks

Several caveats were highlighted. Metrics tied to explicit tokens (e.g., counting the string “Correction:”) bias comparisons in favour of engineered AI outputs. Exhaustive automated detection can raise false positives and cognitive load, so precision and recall must be quantified. Domain-specific risk was emphasised: unverified terminology changes or confidently stated but incorrect medical suggestions present safety hazards unless human verification is mandated (Bélisle-Pipon, 2024). Recent methods for detecting hallucinations and estimating uncertainty were cited as one mitigation avenue (Farquhar et al., 2024). Generalizability was limited by the single LLM, fixed prompts, one cohort, and a sample size of fifty essays.

Future direction

Subsequent research was recommended to measure downstream pedagogical effects of hybrid workflows (revision uptake, learning trajectories, assessment fairness), to quantify per-category precision and recall, to validate terminology corrections against authoritative glossaries or expert raters, and to optimise prompt structure to maximise signal while minimising verbosity. Usability testing with instructors and ethical guardrails (transparent disclosure of AI origin, mandatory human review for domain-sensitive corrections) were argued to be essential before wide deployment (Escalante et al., 2023; Meyer et al., 2024; Farquhar et al., 2024).

Conclusion

Structured LLM prompting was found to produce standardised, comprehensive, and machine-parsable diagnostics suitable for scalable formative tasks; minimalist prompting was useful for quick mechanical edits; and human teachers remained essential for higher-order, contextualised guidance. Hybrid human–AI workflows were proposed as the most promising application, with empirical evaluation of their impacts on student revisions, learning trajectories, and assessment fairness recommended.

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